

ity was 100% for Phostoxin and 67.8% for Lanirat. In the second test, up to 21 d after treatment, 17 out of 19 (89.5%) control burrows were reopened. Seven out of 20 (35%) and 15 out of 20 (75%) Phostoxin- and Lanirat-treated burrows were reopened, respectively. Rat mortality was estimated at 60.9% for Phostoxin and only 16.2% for Lanirat. In the third test, up to 11 d after treatment, 100% of the control burrows were reopened, while five out of 32 (15.6%) Phostoxin-treated burrows were reopened. Rat mortality because of the Phostoxin treatment was estimated at 84.4%.

On average, Phostoxin pellets that produce lethal aluminum phosphide gas achieved 81.8% rat control, whereas the chronic poison Lanirat (bromadiolone) achieved 42%. The test revealed that targeting rats in the burrows during ripening, when most other traditional techniques are ineffective, is a good option. However, of the two chemical rodenticides tested, Phostoxin was much better than Lanirat in achieving immediate population knockdown. The technique of placing the bait or gas-releasing pellets inside the rat burrows should have the least effect on nontarget organisms and on the environment. There-

fore, such a technique could be used in integrated or ecological rodent management programs, if needed.

References

- Catling HD, Islam Z. 1999. Pests of deepwater rice and their management. *Integr. Pest Manage. Rev.* 4:193-229.
- Islam Z, Karim ANMR. 1995. Rat control by trapping in deepwater rice. *Int. J. Pest Manage.* 41(4): 229-233.
- Islam Z, Morton RG, Jupp BP. 1993. The effect of rat damage on deepwater rice yields in Bangladesh. *Int. J. Pest Manage.* 39(2):250-254.
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First report of sheath brown rot of rice in China and characterization of the causal organism by phenotypic tests and Biolog

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A bacterial disease of rice was observed in autumn of 1998-99 in the fields of Jiaxing and Yuhang, Zhejiang Province, China. Oblong to irregular dark green and water-soaked lesions occurred on the sheath, which later became gray-brown or brown surrounded by an effuse dark brown margin. With severe infection, the entire leaf sheath became necrotic and dried out. The panicles withered. Glumes of panicle emerging from the infected sheath exhibited water-soaked lesions that turned light brown. Grains of infected panicles were discolored, deformed, or empty. No bacterial ooze was produced from any part of the infected plant. The disease was first discovered in Japan in

the 1950s. Since then, it has been reported in Southeast Asia, South America, and Africa, but not previously in China (Tanii et al 1976, Xie 1996). However, an epiphytic bacterium isolated from a weed was identified as *Pseudomonas fuscovaginae* in central China in 1986 but not from rice (Duan and Fang 1986). We therefore determined the causal organism and compared it with *P. fuscovaginae*, the causal organism of sheath brown rot of rice, and other related bacteria.

Six and 12 samples of rice grains and plants (5-6 g sample⁻¹) with sheath brown rot were collected from Jiaxing and Yuhang, respectively, in 1998-99. Isolations were done by plating serial dilu-

tion of seed washes (10⁻³-10⁻⁵ g⁻¹) on King's medium B (KMB). Colony morphology was described and phenotypic and pathogenicity tests were performed (Mew and Misra 1994, Xie 1996). Six standard reference strains (I06235 *P. fuscovaginae*, I7007 *P. fuscovaginae*, I9801 *P. fuscovaginae*, I11332B *P. fluorescens* A, I04937 *P. fluorescens* C, and I10278 *P. putida* A1) were provided by IRRI. Additionally, Biolog (Biolog Inc., Hayward, USA) with software version 3.5 was used to further characterize the isolates.

Ten bacterial isolates from samples with sheath brown rot showed characteristics similar to those of the reference strains of

Table 1. Major bacteriological characteristics of causal organism of rice bacterial sheath brown rot compared with related bacteria.^a

Bacteriological test	Strains tested			Reference strains		
	JX	YH	<i>Fus</i>	<i>Flu A</i>	<i>Flu C</i>	<i>Puti</i>
Gram staining	-	-	-	-	-	-
Polar flagellum	+	+	+	+	+	+
Motility	+	+	+	+	+	+
Production of endosporium	-	-	-	-	-	-
Fluorescent pigment	+	+	+	+	+	+
Growth at 41 °C	-	-	-	-	-	-
Oxidation of glucose	+	+	+	+	+	+
Gelatin liquefaction	+	+	+	+	+	-
Nitrate reduction	-	-	-	-	+	-
Levan formation from sucrose	-	-	-	+	-	-
β-glucosidase	-	d	-	-	-	-
Arginine dihydrolase	+	+	+	+	+	+
Lecithinase	d	d	d	+	+	-
Tween 80 lipolysis	d	d	d	+	d	d
Starch hydrolysis	d	d	d	-	-	-
Use of						
L-arabinose	+	+	+	+	-	+
Trehalose	+	+	+	+	+	-
2-ketogluconate	-	-	-	+	+	+
Inositol	-	-	-	+	+	-
Sorbitol	-	-	-	+	+	-
Adonitol	-	-	-	+	+	-
Polygalacturonic acid	-	-	-	-	-	-
Acid production from						
Inulin	-	-	-	-	-	-
Glucose	+	+	+	+	+	+
Mannitol	+	d	+	+	+	+
Salicin	-	-	-	-	-	-
Raffinose	-	-	-	-	-	-
Maltose	-	-	-	-	-	-
Sucrose	-	-	-	-	-	-
Dextrin	-	-	-	-	-	-
Mannose	+	+	+	-	-	-
Hypersensitivity of tobacco	+	+	+	-	-	-
Total strains tested	5	5	3	1	1	1

^a*Fus* = *P. fuscovaginae*, *Flu A* = *P. fluorescens A*, *Flu C* = *P. fluorescens C*, *Puti* = *P. putida A1*. JX = isolated from rice grains collected from Jiaxing; YH = isolated from rice grains collected from Yuhang. + = 80% of the strains were positive; d = 20–80% of the strains were negative; - = means 80% of the strains were negative.

P. fuscovaginae in the phenotypic, pathogenicity, and Biolog tests. The bacterium has the bacillus form, was Gram-negative with 1–4 polar flagella and aerobic, and it produced a green-fluorescent diffusible pigment on KMB. Colonies on nutrient agar medium were white to cream-white and translucent. Table 1 shows 32 phenotypic characteristics of the isolates, which are similar to those of the reference strains of *P. fuscovaginae*. Gelatin liquefac-

tion, nitrate reduction, levan formation from sucrose, and the use of L-arabinose, trehalose, 2-ketogluconate, inositol, sorbitol, and adonitol differentiated the test strain from *P. fluorescens* and *P. putida*. The 10 selected strains isolated from rice grains and plants with sheath brown rot were identified as *P. fuscovaginae* by Biolog, which conformed with the three reference strains of *P. fuscovaginae* having a similarity of 0.819–0.903 (Table 2).

The causal organism of sheath brown rot of rice in Zhejiang Province has been phenotypically identified as *P. fuscovaginae*. It was the same organism reported in Japan in 1976 (Tanii et al 1976) but was different from bacterial sheath rot of rice caused by *P. syringae* (*P. oryzaicola*), which occurred in the province in the 1960s (Fang and Ren 1960).

Table 2. Biolog identification and pathogenicity test for the causal organism of sheath brown rot of rice.

Strain code	Original identification	Biolog identity	Biolog similarity	Incidence at booting stage ^a (%)
I06235	<i>P. fuscovaginae</i>	<i>P. fuscovaginae</i>	0.884	100
I7007	<i>P. fuscovaginae</i>	<i>P. fuscovaginae</i>	0.819	100
I9801	<i>P. fuscovaginae</i>	<i>P. fuscovaginae</i>	0.903	100
I11332B	<i>P. fluorescens</i> A	<i>P. fluorescens</i> A	0.837	0
I04937	<i>P. fluorescens</i> C	<i>P. fluorescens</i> C	0.982	0
I10278	<i>P. putida</i> A1	<i>P. putida</i> A1	0.910	0
CB 97801		<i>P. fuscovaginae</i>	0.794	100
CB 97803		<i>P. fuscovaginae</i>	0.604	100
CB 97805		<i>P. fuscovaginae</i>	0.907	100
CB 97806		<i>P. fuscovaginae</i>	0.741	100
CB 97815		<i>P. fuscovaginae</i>	0.981	100
CB 98801		<i>P. fuscovaginae</i>	0.979	100 (80)
CB 98814		<i>P. fuscovaginae</i>	0.845	100 (80)
CB 98817		<i>P. fuscovaginae</i>	0.939	100 (70)
CB 98818		<i>P. fuscovaginae</i>	0.926	100 (60)
CB 98820		<i>P. fuscovaginae</i>	0.837	100 (90)
Distilled water	-	-	-	0

^aInjection inoculation was used at booting stage; 10 rice plants per strain. Numbers in parentheses are results of spray inoculation with 10 rice plants per strain.

References

- Duan YP, Fang ZD. 1986. Identification of bacterial stripe of cereal crop. *Acta Phytopathol. Sin.* 16(4):228-235.
- Fang CT, Ren HC. 1960. A bacterial disease of rice new to China. *Acta Phytopathol. Sin.* 6(1):90-92.
- Mew TW, Misra JK. 1994. A manual of rice seed health testing. Manila (Philippines): International Rice Research Institute. 220 p.
- Tanii A, Miyajima K, Akita T. 1976. The sheath brown rot disease of rice plant and its causal bacterium, *Pseudomonas fuscovaginae*, A. Tanii, K. Miyajima, T. Akita sp. nov. *Ann. Phytopathol. Soc. Jpn.* 42(5):540-548.
- Xie GL. 1996. Characterization of *Pseudomonas* spp. and other bacterial species associated with rice seeds. PhD thesis, University of the Philippines Los Baños, Philippines. 170 p.

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